

Interference Evaluation on Software Defined Radio Links using the Amplitude Probability Distribution

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Abstract—In this study, Universal Software Radio Peripherals are employed to set configurable wireless radio links in the presence of intentionally generated electromagnetic disturbances. The receiving end of the radio link is used to measure the interfered demodulated signal. The amplitude probability distribution of the receiver output is calculated using a generalized formulation. The measurements have been validated and adjusted using an oscilloscope-based time-domain electromagnetic emissions measurement system with calibrated and compliant characteristics. The results showed that the Software Defined Radio devices could be used to perform probability distribution measurements, obtaining coherent and accurate results with respect to the amplitude and the respective probabilities for the type of disturbance applied in each case.

Keywords—amplitude probability distribution, electromagnetic emissions, electromagnetic interference, software defined radios, wireless communications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wireless systems are critical for leveraging applications such as smart cities, smart grids, autonomous vehicles, and the Internet of Things. Due to the rapid expansion of radio-enabled devices and the increasingly polluted electromagnetic spectrum, the risk of electromagnetic interference (EMI) has grown, increasing the likelihood of loss of performance and compromising the reliability of communication links [1] [2]. This problem is even more evident in the Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM) bands, where many devices simultaneously engage in high-throughput communications.

In this regard, it has been argued that standard methodologies for electromagnetic emissions assessment, particularly those involving the quasi-peak (QP) detector, may not adequately protect existing digital communication systems [3].

In [4], the limitations of current electromagnetic emissions test methods and requirements are discussed, emphasizing the potential of the Amplitude Probability Distribution (APD) as a more relevant metric for evaluating EMI in this context. However, even though modern measuring receivers may include the APD function as per the CISPR 16-1-1 [5], to date,

APD measurements are generally not required for emissions testing.

The APD definition, as proposed in [4], is more general and flexible and allows for alternative measuring instruments, providing a completely digital implementation of the APD calculation algorithm. For example, Software Defined Radios (SDR) receivers can be used for this purpose, and this is convenient because they are widely available at relatively low costs. In this regard, Universal Software Radio Peripherals (USRP) are highly configurable and versatile SDR development systems. USRPs have been used in other studies such as [6] and [7].

In brief, this paper uses the revised definition of the APD measuring function given in [4] and implements it to evaluate the impact of EMI in SDR based links using USRPs. First, Section II summarizes the generalized APD function and its algorithm, focusing on the EMI processing. Then, Section III explains the methodology applied during the experiments, and Section IV presents the corresponding experimental results. Finally, the paper closes with some conclusions and hints for future work.

II. GENERALIZED APD MEASURING FUNCTION

The diagram of the generalized APD function is shown in Fig. 1. In this section, we will explain each step of the corresponding measurement processing.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the generalized APD measuring function for a received signal.

This APD calculation algorithm is based on direct-sampling techniques. The continuous waveform $x(t)$ is sampled at full bandwidth using high-resolution ADCs. Then, a digital filter bank (DFB) decomposes the digitized input $x[t]$, into n parallel signals, $x_k[t]$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, each one characterized by a bandwidth and centre frequency selected according to the specifications of the wireless system

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to be protected. Afterwards, digital down conversion (DDC) is performed to extract the I/Q components in baseband. The I/Q components are subsequently employed to calculate the corresponding signal envelope, $x_{k,\text{env}}[t]$. Next, the k -th envelope is resampled, and the resulting samples are used to find their probability density function using the Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) method. Ultimately, the APD is calculated at any amplitude level.

Regarding the envelope resampling block, we propose using a nonuniform scheme, interpolating the envelope amplitude at randomised time instants, \mathbf{t}_{rs} [8]. This is important because it allows for extracting more information regarding the amplitude distribution of the envelope and reduces unwanted correlations due to repetitive points and periodicity effects. Such randomization can be obtained by adding a controlled jitter to a uniformly spaced time vector, that is,

$$\mathbf{t}_{\text{rs}} = \mathbf{t} + \boldsymbol{\tau} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{t} = \{t_1, t_1 + \Delta t, t_1 + 2\Delta t, \dots, t_1 + N\Delta t\}$ is a set of exact time instants for each envelope point produced at a regular period, Δt , and $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \{\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_N\}$ is the additive jitter randomly generated within the $\pm\Delta t/2$ interval for each envelope point. For performing the envelope interpolation, the modified Akima algorithm is recommended [9].

The output of the resampling block is a set of envelope amplitude values $\mathbf{X}_{k,\text{env}} = \{X_{(k,\text{env}),1}, X_{(k,\text{env}),2}, \dots, X_{(k,\text{env}),N}\}$. The distribution of $X_{k,\text{env}}$ is unknown, but it can be estimated using $\mathbf{X}_{k,\text{env}}$ through the occurrences of the random variable $X_{k,\text{env}}$. Instead of using the histogram method, we recommend the KDE approach. The KDE is a non-parametric statistical technique used to estimate the pdf of a continuous random variable. The core idea of KDE is to estimate the density of a random variable by placing a “kernel” function at each data point and then summing these kernel functions to obtain an estimate of the pdf, as given in (2). The kernel function is usually a smooth, symmetric probability density function, such as the Gaussian or Epanechnikov kernel, which is centred at each data point and smoothed according to the parameter h , which determines how wide or narrow the kernel is.

$$\hat{f}_{k,\text{env}}(x) = \frac{1}{Nh} \sum_{j=1}^N K\left(\frac{X_{k,\text{env}} - X_{(k,\text{env}),j}}{h}\right) \quad (2)$$

Afterwards, the cdf is evaluated at certain amplitude threshold values, $x_{k,\text{th}}$, as

$$F_{k,\text{env}}(x_{k,\text{th}}) = \int_{-\infty}^{x_{k,\text{th}}} \hat{f}_{k,\text{env}}(x) dx, \quad (3)$$

where $x_{k,\text{th}}$ should be evenly distributed using a bin width calculated using a statistical criterion and within a range that allows reaching the required probability levels. For instance, Scott’s rule is often a good rule of thumb in this regard [10]. Finally, $F_{k,\text{env}}(x_{k,\text{th}})$ is inputted into

$$APD_{X_{\text{env}}}(x) = 1 - F_{X_{\text{env}}}(x) \quad (4)$$

for obtaining $APD_{X_{k,\text{env}}}(x_{k,\text{th}})$.

III. METHODOLOGY

The generalized APD’s applicability for EMI assessments using SDR links is experimentally evaluated, focusing on understanding the influence of various disturbance types on the statistical distribution of the received signal. The experiment design, the transmitting output waveform verification, and the test setup are described in detail in the following sections.

A. Wireless signal generation

Using MATLAB WLAN Toolbox, a WiFi baseband waveform according to the standard IEEE 802.11g was generated and configured as non-high-throughput (non-HT) with a modulation and coding scheme of 64-QAM with 3/4 rate. The signal with a PSDU length of 2048 bytes was defined with a bandwidth and sampling frequency of 20 MHz and the message was generated with a random sequence of bits. Fig. 2 shows the main parts of the waveform. Before $2\mu\text{s}$, the preamble consists of three legacy segments: the short and long training fields, L-STF and L-LTF, respectively, and the signal field, L-SIG. Then, after $2\mu\text{s}$, there is the data.

Fig. 2. Example of a generated WiFi waveform according to the standard IEEE 802.11g configured as non-HT.

B. Experimental setup

The experiment required establishing a WiFi link over the air between the transmitting (Tx) and receiving (Rx) USRPs units (National Instruments USRP-2901, 70 MHz to 6 GHz), while some controlled radiated disturbances were generated in-band. A diagram of the test setup is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Diagram of the experimental setup.

The experiment was performed inside a compact 3 m measurement distance full anechoic chamber at GCEM UPC to create a controllable electromagnetic environment. The setup included some suitable antennas, a pair of PCs used to configure, read and store the data from the respective USRPs, an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) model 81150A from Keysight used as the source for the interference, and a 1 GHz bandwidth real-time sampling oscilloscope model DPO5104B from Tektronix used for validation. The oscilloscope was used in conjunction with EMC Barcelona’s emiGO software v2.0 to enable EMI measurements according to the CISPR 16-1-1 baseline parameters. The photo in Fig. 4 shows the setup with all the devices in place.

Fig. 4. Experimental setup. Antennas, USRPs and other elements are depicted.

C. Experimental design

The APD of the transmitted signal is evaluated in different iterations of the experiment where certain radiated interference is applied. Each of those disturbances has distinctive characteristics according to the waveform type and parameters. Such characteristics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. EMI characteristics

Experiment ID	Waveform type	EMI type	Waveform parameters
B1	Sine	In-band narrowband	Frequency range = 301 MHz RMS amplitude = 1V
A1	WGN	Continuous broadband	RMS amplitude = 100 mV
A2			RMS amplitude = 500 mV
C1	Chirp	Broadband pulsed	Frequency range = 100 - 500 MHz Period = 10 ms RMS amplitude = 100 mV
C2			Frequency range = 100 - 500 MHz Period = 2 ms RMS amplitude = 100 mV
D1			Frequency range = 250 - 350MHz Period = 10 ms RMS amplitude = 100 mV

Furthermore, the gain setting on the Tx and Rx USRP units is set to 50 dB, while the USRP’s centre frequency was set to 300 MHz due to instrumentation constraints.

IV. RESULTS

This section summarizes the outcomes of the experiments. With respect to the results, it is important to remark that we performed a level settling adjustment for correcting the absolute values directly measured with the USRP_{Rx} with respect to those measured with the oscilloscope when a reference sinewave input signal was applied. Moreover, we checked the linearity of the measurements and that the USRP_{Rx} was not overloading during the experiments.

A. Reference measurement

Fig. 5 shows the APD without any signal or disturbance (Tx off) and the APD with the USRP_{Tx} active (Tx on). The Tx off (red dashed) trace corresponds to the receiver noise at the configured gain (50 dB) and bandwidth conditions (20 MHz). The receiver noise threshold at a probability level of 10^{-7} is approximately 67 dB μ V. The Tx on (blue) trace is the APD measured when turning on the RF output of USRP_{Tx}. In such conditions, the APD is shifted to the right, and the signal level at the lowest probability level measured is 92 dB μ V.

Fig. 5. Measurement of APD reference values.

B. In-band narrowband EMI

Fig. 6 depicts the received spectrum in the experimental condition B1, in-band narrowband EMI, with and without WiFi signal. The spectrum is measured from 285 MHz to 315 MHz using a resolution bandwidth of 120 kHz. The peak amplitude of the disturbance is about 113 dB μ V, while the WiFi signal level is about 69 dB μ V.

Fig. 6. Spectrum of the received disturbance voltage for the in-band narrowband EMI.

Since WiFi APD is Gaussian-like, when the measurement bandwidth is changed from 120 kHz to 20 MHz in order to match the WiFi channel bandwidth, the signal level is increased proportionally 22 dB. This estimation corresponds very well with the measured APD as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. APD of the received WiFi signal and the in-band narrowband disturbance.

As expected, results show how the APD from the received signal is modified due to the influence of the narrowband interference. In this case, the level of the disturbance applied is so high with respect to the signal that the EMI dominates the resulting statistical distribution. This points to a severe case of interference, confirmed because the information can not be retrieved while the disturbance remains active.

C. White Gaussian Noise

The following experiment uses WGN to exercise the APD measurement under broadband and continuous disturbance. In this case, the disturbance has an amplitude distribution similar to that of the signal. Fig. 8 presents the spectrum of the signal with the disturbance active for test cases A1 and A2. There, the WiFi signal is still recognizable in the blue trace, but its spectrum is noisier, while the green trace corresponds to a situation where the added noise level is masking the signal.

Fig. 8. Spectrum of the received WiFi signal with added WGN.

Again, the impact of the applied disturbance can be seen in the APD diagram. When the broadband disturbance level is significantly lower than the signal level (A1), the resulting

APD is not largely deformed with respect to one of the signals but already denotes the some reduction of the signal-to-noise ratio. In fact, in the A1 Tx case, the largest deviations in the APD correspond to the lower probability levels, which may indicate a BER in the order of 10^{-5} .

Fig. 9. APD of the received WiFi signal with additive white Gaussian noise as broadband and continuous disturbance.

In the more aggressive scenario (A2 Tx), the measured APD is completely shifted to the right; thus, the useful signal is destroyed. The amplitudes in the APD diagrams in Fig. 9 for A1 and A2 at a probability of 10^{-7} are 90 dB and 104 dB. The difference of 14 dB between the most and least severe cases agrees with the increase of the disturbance level at the output of the signal generator.

D. Chirp pulse

This condition evaluates the scenario of a chirp pulse as a representative case of broadband discontinuous EMI. In the C1 and C2 cases, the chirp frequency sweeps linearly a range of 400 MHz, from 100 MHz to 500 MHz. This means the disturbance is only in-band during 5% of the time. From the receiver's standpoint, the disturbance is pulsed with the said duty cycle. Fig. 10 shows the overlapped disturbance and signal spectrum for those cases.

Fig. 10. Spectrum of the Rx WiFi signal with disturbances C1 and C2.

On the other hand, as indicated in Table 1, in the case D1 the chirp period was kept as in C1, 10 ms, but the span of the chirp was reduced to 100 MHz, so the EMI duty is 20%.

Fig. 11 displays the spectrum for the respective cases of the experiment.

Fig. 11. Spectrum of the Rx WiFi signal with disturbances C1 and D1.

Fig. 12 shows the waveforms of the received disturbances for cases C1, C2 and D1 and confirms the expected pulsed EMI behaviour in the receiver end.

Fig. 12. Received disturbances measured in the time-domain for test cases C1, C2, and D1.

Fig. 13. APD of the received WiFi signal in the presence of broadband pulsed EMI for the test cases of C1, C2 and D1.

Fig. 13 gathers the APD measured for the test cases of C1, C2 and D1, that is, those where the chirp pulse is used to emulate a broadband discontinuous EMI. In all cases, the APD exhibits the characteristic shape of the impulsive type of noise. The APD plots for cases C1 and C2 overlap as their duty cycle is 5%. Conversely, as the duty of D1 is 20%, it can be clearly distinguished above C1 and C2. In all cases, the measured probability of high and low disturbance levels are accurate as they exactly correspond to the EMI duty cycle. The APD results show a visual relationship between communication signal degradation and the prevalence of the applied disturbance.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The APD measurement using the USRPs delivered coherent results using different types of EMI, with excellent estimations for the required probability levels and distributions. After the appropriate configuration and adjustment, the USRP readings measured accurate signal levels comparable to those from the calibrated real-time oscilloscope used as a validation reference.

From the experiments, the influence of the EMI on the WiFi signal is analyzed. The main observations are: 1) the APD of the signal, in the absence of the disturbance, follows the expected Gaussian-like distribution 2) The applied disturbances modify the APD of the signal, and given an increasingly higher EMI level, the statistical distribution observed at the Rx end becomes similar to the APD of the applied disturbance. 3) A good indication of communication quality degradation is the deformation of the APD of the received signal. 4) The APD evaluation under the chirp disturbance condition shows that once a certain amplitude threshold is exceeded, the impact of the broadband EMI is more related to the duration of the EMI burst and not that much to the repetition frequency. Therefore, increasing the duty cycle of the chirp disturbances results in a greater negative impact, to the point the received signal is completely degraded.

Finally, this study supports the idea that USRPs and software-defined radios are helpful and resourceful tools for EMI assessment in wireless communications. They provide a flexible and low-cost platform for setting wireless communication links while measuring the received electromagnetic disturbance and its impact on communication quality.

This investigation will be expanded to include digital quality communication metrics in future works.

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